

Novafert

Deliverable 5.3 – Report on Regional Working Groups establishment in each NOVAFERT Region

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Executive Summary

The objective of this document is to describe the process followed to establish 7 Regional Working Groups (RWGs) in the participant European regions to engage stakeholders from target countries and create a broader Community of Practice for the use of alternative fertilisers.

NOVAFERT RWGs are intended to be groups of regional actors related to the value chain of the waste stream(s) associated with each region and the agricultural / farming sector, willing to contribute to the alternative fertilisers' development and implementation. Their opinions, views, experiences, doubts, etc. have been / will be gathered, discussed and developed, contributing to the creation of regional clusters.

Following a multi-actor approach, relevant stakeholders from targeted regions have been identified and contacted from the very beginning of the project and have been (and will be) involved in a variety of activities: elaboration of the SWOT and the PEST analysis (WP3), elaboration of Regional Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) (WP3), selecting and/or visiting the lighthouse demos (WP4), attending the participatory workshops (WP5), attending the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) (WP6), etc. By the time the present deliverable was submitted, the stakeholders have participated in two main activities: the initial introduction of the project, being requested to become RWG members, and the elaboration of the SWOT and the PEST analyses (WP3), activity in which their contribution has been absolutely relevant. The RWGs will be also involved in other tasks with regional scope to consolidate clusters in each region, with the aim of making them permanent after the project ending. It is the consortium members' aim to continue enlarging the regional network of stakeholders interested in nutrient recovery and alternative fertilisers and operating in the target countries during the project lifetime and beyond.

To effectively create these RWGs, the RWG leaders were requested to establish an initial core group with habitual colleagues or collaborators related to the value chain of their associated waste streams or to the agricultural / farming sector. The aim was to start this work with 3-4 close and engaged collaborators aiming to identify and mobilise other stakeholders. Once these core groups were created, additional stakeholders were contacted and asked to be part of the RWGs, thus enlarging these structures as desired.

To achieve this, different introduction meetings were held, introducing the project and its aims to the stakeholders and asking for their participation. Several of these meetings have been reported in this deliverable.

Afterwards, once the groups had a considerable size, they were convened to bigger meetings, where concrete NOVAFERT activities like the SWOT analysis were conducted, counting with their views and contributions. Several of these meetings have been also reported in this deliverable.

It is the aim of all partners to continue interacting with the RWGs and counting with their contributions for many upcoming activities until the end of the project. The present deliverable reports the activities conducted since month 3 until month 15, the time in which the RWGs have been created. Although the creation task finalises in month 15, it is expected to continue organising meetings and consulting them until the end of the project in month 36.

The stakeholders groups have been tailored for each region according to their associated waste streams as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. NOVAFERT regions and their associated waste streams

1. Introduction

One of the main objectives of NOVAFERT project is to set up 7 Regional Working Groups (RWGs) in the participant European regions to lead the transition towards the bioeconomy throughout the EU within the interconnected tasks in WP3 and WP5, and will be achieved through the successful implementation of five tasks, one of which we are focusing on in this deliverable:

- Task 5.2: Cross-network collaboration – establishment of RWGs (November 2022 – November 2023).

These RWGs are intended to engage relevant stakeholders of the target regions in the implementation of alternative fertilising solutions, serving as an important mechanism for gathering knowledge and opinions to contribute to the preparation and implementation of the Region Specific Action Plans (RSAPs) to be developed under task 3.3. RWGs will be also involved in other tasks with regional scope. A RWG has been organised in each of the target regions of the project, being led by the corresponding regional NOVAFERT consortium partner.

The stakeholders have been identified and contacted from the very beginning of the project to involve them in the definition of the strategies and following a multi-actor approach, and this work will continue until the end of the project duration. Each RWG is aimed to organise at least four meetings (face to face or online) per region, i.e., at least 28 meetings in total during the project frame.

The consortium partners are trying to include a balanced representation of stakeholders from the target groups identified per each region according to their associated targeted secondary raw materials. The RWGs are facilitated by a representative from the concerned NOVAFERT project partner to oversee the group operation.

It is expected that these RWGs will comprehend its start-up, preparation, discussions and dynamics to promote a participatory process and the engagement of all members, and follow-up actions in order to create permanent clusters in each of the target regions of the project.

2. What is a Regional Working Group?

The overall objective of the RWGs is to gather relevant knowledge and opinions that contribute to the preparation and implementation of the RSAPs to be developed within task 3.3.

Prior to the establishment of the RWGs, the NOVAFERT project has performed for each of the NOVAFERT concerned regions a screening of the relevant data and figures on a range of fertilising products near to be put into practice and a mapping of EU-nutrient recycling open innovation systems, that will be followed by the elaboration of recycled N&P products and ready for practice technologies.

This collection of information will be used to engage identified stakeholders in the RWGs and will be used to stimulate discussions within the RWGs. It will serve to promote the joint development of strategic thinking, the two-way exchange of ideas between the different stakeholders and will also feed with practical recommendations for the formulation of the RSAPs (task 3.3).

2.1. Structure and composition of the RWGs

NOVAFERT community is aimed to be based on the Quadruple Helix Model of Innovation, which recognises four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society. It is an innovation and collaboration model with a citizen/end-user perspective. The model is useful in innovation processes where the citizens' needs are central.

Using the Quadruple Helix and involving the citizens/end-users in the development of an innovation can led to more successful, user-oriented innovations. The end users will be more likely to accept and use the innovation. It will also have a greater social benefit at a lower cost and improve empowerment of the citizens, who will increasingly experience trust towards the innovators and become an active part of the innovation system.

Figure 2. Quadruple Helix Model of Innovation

Considering the Quadruple Helix initial common classification, each RWG has to define (and further include a balanced representation in the RWG) the most relevant target groups within each of the four helixes according to their region and their targeted secondary raw materials.

2.2. Functioning of the RWGs

The facilitator from each RWG is encouraged to enrol the stakeholders in the active participation in RWG meetings, preparing a set of topics to be discussed and the activities to be implemented following a multi-actor participatory approach. This can be done after a discussion with the RWG core group, facilitating a consensus on the topics to be discussed during the meeting. This could contribute to actively engage the stakeholders from the beginning.

It is vital that the objectives and the expected outcomes of the RWGs are perfectly clear to all members that take part in the meetings and that the roles of engagement are also clear. The members of the RWGs, according to the DoA, have to:

- Propose practical recommendations for the formulation of the RSAPs (task 3.3).
- Disseminate intensively at local and regional level the NOVAFERT project results and outcomes through their own communication channels.
- Be engaged in the implementation of alternative fertilising solutions.
- Seek new opportunities to perform cooperative activities.

- Create permanent clusters in each NOVAFERT target region to adopt and disseminate alternative fertilising solutions.

2.3. Role and responsibilities of the RWG leader

The RWG facilitator is an individual belonging to the corresponding regional consortium partner. The main responsibilities of the facilitator are:

Table 1. RWG leader role and responsibilities

Responsibility	Expected Contributions	Outputs
Setting-up the RWG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invite and enrol active members (multi-actor approach). - Prepare topics for discussion. - Plan activities (participatory approach). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invitation letter/e-mail to potential members. - Prepare the program of the meetings.
Running the RWG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain the objectives and expected outcomes of the RWGs and members expected responsibilities. - Oversee the meetings run as planned. - Ensure that all members actively participate in the discussion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report with practical recommendations for the formulation of the Regional Action Plans (task 3.3).
Communication and outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise and contribute to communication and dissemination activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Send inputs for the NOVAFERT website (brief description of the RWGs, members, calendar of events, scientific articles, news, etc.). - Publish at least 1 social media post per RWG meeting (before, during or immediately after). - Register RWGs members as followers of the NOVAFERT social media accounts and relay

		social media posts published by the central communication team to increase outreach.
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3. Identification of stakeholders for the RWGs

The identification of relevant stakeholders for NOVAFERT RWGs has been conducted in two steps based on the immediacy of the contact:

Step 1: immediate sources already identified:

- Own network of contacts.
- FER-PLAY project.
- Sources of information mentioned in the DoA:
 - EU projects: nutrient recycling-oriented EU-projects and Thematic networks, like NUTRIMAN, JRC's STRUBIAS project, SAFEMANURE.
 - EU Platforms and Associations: Biorefine Cluster Europe, ESPP, EBA, other EU-nutrient platforms.

Step 2: additional sources checked:

- EU, national and regional related projects.
- Regional sectorial operational groups (like the [EIP-AGRI Operational Groups Database](#)).
- Professional (when possible, regional) sectorial associations.
- Regional researchers / research groups.
- Regional public administration with competencies on the sector.
- Published best practices: atlas, compendiums or any other type of compilations (from sources like the [European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#), among others).
- Sectorial events (annual / biannual conferences or fairs, etc.)

3.1. Initial members: the core group

In order to start the work, the partners established an initial core group with those colleagues or collaborators of the sector with which they are used to work. This core group has been the basis to further establish the RWGs.

The core group is integrated by at least 3-4 different stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix, and has been further enlarged thanks to the stakeholders identified. However,

this core group remains being important, as it constitutes the first “consulting body” with regards to any activity to be further organised at regional level.

3.2. Final RWGs composition

After the core group has been established, the partners have been contacting stakeholders and asking them to be part of our RWGs.

It is important to highlight this will be an active task until the end of the project, and there will be no limit to include members; the bigger the RWG is, the better, considering one of the main aims of the project is creating permanent clusters in each NOVAFERT target region to adopt and disseminate alternative fertilising solutions. The rest of the activities to be done during the project will also help to enlarge these RWGs.

4. Documents and tools created to manage the RWGs

Different documents have been created to support the partners in the compilation of information and also to further store it and present it in a homogeneous way.

4.1. Stakeholders’ regional lists

BIOAZUL created an Excel document with the aim of collating all information regarding the stakeholders identified. It was created and updated to SharePoint, so all partners could have it accessible in case of need.

It was created with the aim of being useful for other activities of other work packages as well, avoiding this way repeating the same initial steps for different tasks, so it compiles basic but useful information.

The Excel file has one sheet per region, even including an additional sheet for other EU regions / countries, as well as another one including the automatic data feeding the table.

Andalusia (ES)											
Type of stakeholder	Gender	Source of information	List of references about description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	In the scope of information related to: -EU projects -national projects -regional projects -name of the project	List of references of name of the project (if applicable)	Surname	Name	E-mail address	Entity	Position	Location
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Reyes	José	jose@novafert.com	TR091	Company manager	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Morales Rodríguez	Morales Rodríguez	morales@novafert.com	TR091	Labourer	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Fernández Gómez	José	jose@novafert.com	TR091	Labourer	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	García Morera	José	jose@novafert.com	TR091	Builder	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Esteban Rodríguez	José	jose@novafert.com	TR091	Labourer	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Sanchez Argente	Ismael	ismael@novafert.com	TR091	Agri-technical register	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Winkelberg	Miriam	miriam@novafert.com	TR091	Counsellor for food safety register	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Palacios Tello	Sherazade Marz	sherazade@novafert.com	TR091	Agri-technical technician	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	EU project	2.26.000	Mora Marín	Adrián	adrian@novafert.com	TR091	Agri-technical register	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in FEDER project	EU project	2.26.000	López Rodríguez	Marcos	marcos@novafert.com	TR091	Quality and food safety technician	Vitoria-Medina
Business - Large company	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in FEDER project	EU project	2.26.000	Brown Egler	José Manuel	jmanuel@novafert.com	TR091	Meeting Board Member	Vitoria-Medina
Foundation	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in FEDER project	EU project	2.26.000	Gilmore Carrero	Ángel	angel@novafert.com	CETABOR Red. Local	Project Manager	Madrid
Foundation	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in FEDER project	EU project	2.26.000	Gilmore Carrero	Enrique	enrique@novafert.com	CETABOR Red. Local	Manager	Madrid
Business - SME	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	de Paula Romero	Adrián	adrian@novafert.com	BIORABOR	Manager	Torre del Mar
Business - SME	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Pérez Morera	Rafael	rafael@novafert.com	BIORABOR	Executive board member	Torre del Mar
Business - SME	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Carpes Martínez	Carpes Rodríguez	carpes@novafert.com	BIORABOR	Vice-president	Torre del Mar
Business - SME	Private sector	Other external contact	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	Not applicable		Fernández Rodríguez	Ismael	ismael@novafert.com	Equipek Iberica	Co-founder and CEO	Caceres
Business - SME	Private sector	Other external contact	Minifert is the regional fund requested by ROYALFERT and FEDER projects in Vitoria-Medina, through a contract with the Andalusian region. http://www.novafert.com/financiacion	Not applicable		Mancha Plaza	Enrique	enrique@novafert.com	Equipek Iberica	Sales Director	Caceres
Business - SME	Private sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in FEDER project	EU project	2.26.000	Morales Paricio	Adrián	adrian@novafert.com	Agri-technical Ed.	CEO	Vitoria-Medina
Research center	Public sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Utrera Sánchez	Fernando José	fernando@novafert.com	IMDH L. Medica	Technician	Málaga
Research center	Public sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Benítez Rodríguez	Maria Benítez	maria@novafert.com	IMDH L. Medica	Senior Scientist	Málaga
Research center	Public sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Morales Brown	Isabel	isabel@novafert.com	IMDH L. Medica	Research Professor	Málaga
Research center	Public sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Carrillo Rodríguez	Adrián	adrian@novafert.com	IMDH L. Medica	Manager	Málaga
Local public administration	Public sector	Referral of contacts	Collaboration in BIOBIO project	EU project	BIOBIO	Gil Espinosa	José Manuel	jmanuel@novafert.com	Málaga's Institute of Economic	Manager	Málaga

Figure 3. Excel file for stakeholders data compilation

The fields to be completed are the following:

- **Type of stakeholder.** The type of stakeholder can be chosen from the ones available in the foldable list:
 - Business - Large company
 - Business - SME
 - Business - Start-ups / entrepreneurs
 - Farmers
 - Association
 - Foundation
 - University
 - Technology centre
 - Research centre
 - Local public administration
 - Regional public administration
 - National public administration

- NGO
- Other
- **Sector.** It refers to the sector from the quadruple helix to which the stakeholders belong. They are also included in a foldable list.
 - Private sector
 - Academic sector
 - Public sector
 - Civil society
- **Source of information.** It refers to the source from which the stakeholder information has been extracted. The possible sources are also included in a foldable list.
 - Network of contacts
 - Professional contacts via desk research
 - EU platform
 - National platform
 - Regional platform
 - Regional operational group
 - Regional cluster
 - Published article
 - Published case study
 - Other type of publication
 - Fair
 - Conference
 - Other sectorial event
 - Other
- **Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted.** The kind of information to be included here is a project website, a sectorial event, a case study, etc., or even a description, whatever it is considered more useful.

- **Is the source of information related to any EU project / national project / regional project / none of them?** It refers to the dimension of the initiative identified. The possible sources are also included in a foldable list.
 - EU project
 - National project
 - Regional project
 - Not applicable
- **Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable).** The name of the project, its grant agreement number or any other reference can be included here.
- **Surname.**
- **Name.**
- **E-mail address.**
- **Entity.**
- **Position.**
- **Location.**

The advantage of this table is that it is possible to filter by type of stakeholder, by sector or by source of information (it is possible also to apply a filter in more than one column at the same time), so, for example:

- Using the filter “type of stakeholders” and marking “farmers” could be useful to extract valuable information for WP1 inventories, info that could be exported and enriched according to the tasks needs.
- Using the filter “source of information” and marking “published case study” could be useful to identify potential candidates for WP1 living labs and WP4 lighthouse demos, and this info could be also exported and enlarged.

The sheet “other regions and countries” has an additional column with a foldable list including the EU countries. It is also possible to filter by country in this sheet. Thus, all information that does not belong specifically to NOVAFERT regions but could be considered relevant, could be included in this sheet.

4.2. Information and consent form

As much personal information is requested to the stakeholders, it is necessary to inform them about the concrete information that is going to be demanded (already described

in section 3.1) and how it is going to be used, and it is also necessary to have their consent to have it and use it.

To do so, IMPACT created an information and consent form for stakeholders to join the Regional Working Groups that was prepared according to the current EU legislation (template attached in **Annex 1**). The template was prepared by IMPACT in English, and afterwards it was translated to the regional languages and adapted according to the region needs by the corresponding project partners.

In addition to that, electronic forms were also prepared to facilitate their completion online.

The signature of this consent form is a requisite to be part of the RWG.

The RWG leaders are responsible of compiling and storing their corresponding signed consent forms. SharePoint folders have been also created with this purpose.

5. RWG meetings

As stated in the DoA, the RWGs have to organise frequent meetings during the project timeframe. The leader of each region has to organise at least four meetings, face to face and/or online, with the RWG potential members.

5.1. RWG meetings methodology

In order to actively engage stakeholders during the meetings, there are several tools that follow a participatory methodology and facilitate effective engagement of target stakeholders. The activities aim at promoting the engagement of stakeholders and their collaboration in a participatory approach.

An example of those tools is the [World Café method](#), whose description can be found in the Engage2020 Action Catalogue (an outcome of the EC funded Engage2020 project). It is a method for engaging groups, both within organisations and in the public sphere. This method follows the principle of a good conversation, where anybody is able to talk about things that matter to them, and it is founded on the assumption that people have the capacity to work together, no matter who they are.

The World Café method relies on seven core design principles:

- Set the context.
- Create hospitable space.
- Explore questions that matter.
- Encourage everyone's contribution.
- Cross-pollinate and connect diverse perspectives.

- Listen together for patterns, insights and deeper questions.
- Harvest and share collective discoveries.

The setting should create an environment which is most often modelled like a café (including round tables with 4 or 5 chairs). The host should begin with a welcome and an introduction followed with the first of three (or more) twenty-minute rounds of conversation for the small group seated around a table. After the first round, each member of the small groups moves to another table. One person will stay at the table as table host for the next round and briefly fills them in on what happened in the previous round. Each round of a World Café is prefaced with a question designed for the specific context and desired purpose of the session. After the small groups, the participants are invited to share results from their conversations with the rest of the whole group. These results are reflected visually in a variety of ways, most often using graphic recorders in the front of the room.

The World Café method can create results to generate new ideas, to enable joint decision-making on key strategic issues, to discover new ways for collaboration, to reflect on the implications of a complex issue and to identify specific steps for further exploration and implementation.

These meetings can be conducted in face to face or online modality. There are several online platforms that can be used when face to face meetings are not an option, and these tools still allow the planning of dynamics as described before. Tools such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Google Meet, GoToMeeting or Cisco Webex meetings are just some examples.

There are other methodologies that can be followed, it will always depend on the type of meeting and the purpose of it.

5.2. Engagement of stakeholders during the RWG meetings

Besides the different tools that can be used during the RWG meetings to promote a participatory process and engage stakeholders, there are several methodologies that can contribute to make the meetings more interactive and collaborative:

- Initiate the meeting with an icebreaker. This is particularly important if the participants do not know each other or come from a different background. This can be achieved by asking participants to pick a word that can in some ways define them, what can be then followed by a brief presentation of themselves.
- Promote participatory discussions, where tools like [Pinup](#), [Mural](#) or [Miro](#) can be a powerful instrument to promote debate and discussion. These are visual platforms with intuitive visual collaboration features like sticky notes that make collaboration creative, engaging and productive.

- Launch questionnaires using tools like [Mentimeter](#) or [Sli.do](#), which are live interactive applications to get feedback from the participants that allow to create pools and Q&A's, among others experiences with the participants.
- Network with other meetings' attendees. Networking (during breaks, for example) is a powerful tool for participants to get to know each other and to exchange ideas and experiences.

5.3. Communication with stakeholders after the RWG meetings

After each RWG meeting, it is important to make a follow up communication with the participants to keep them involved with the project and to encourage them to participate in the next RWGs events. This can be easily accomplished with several actions:

- Send an e-mail right after the meeting thanking the participants for attending it.
- Send an e-mail to the participants who did not show or attended and share some of the outcomes of the meeting. This might compel them to participate next time.
- Once the major outcomes of the meeting are prepared, send an e-mail with the major conclusions and results and, if possible, an indication for the next RWG event agenda.

5.4. Record of attendees and main outcomes of the RWG meetings

It is crucial to keep a register of the stakeholders who have participated in the RWG meetings, as well as of the main discussions carried out and the main outcomes of the events.

In this sense, a short report has been prepared after every meeting with one/several RWG member(s), not only to keep track of the outcomes of their discussions, but also to report about this work to the EC.

It is important to mention that at least 4 RWG meetings are mandatory, but more of them can be organised if needed. Moreover, not only formal announced meetings are intended to be reported, but also informal meetings and calls with other members from the RWG.

To facilitate the RWG meetings reporting, a fiche has been prepared by BIOAZUL. It has to be filled in by the RWG responsible and provided to BIOAZUL every time a RWG meeting is held.

[NAME OF THE REGION] REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING					
EVENT	[Name of the event, e.g.: 1 st RWG meeting]				
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	[Day/ Month/ Year – Online] <i>or</i> [Day/ Month/ Year – City, (Country)]				
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	[Name of the facilitator – entity]				
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	[Name]	[Entity]	[Position]	[Stakeholder group]	[E-mail]
	[Name]	[Entity]	[Position]	[Stakeholder group]	[E-mail]
	[Name]	[Entity]	[Position]	[Stakeholder group]	[E-mail]
	[Name]	[Entity]	[Position]	[Stakeholder group]	[E-mail]
	[Name]	[Entity]	[Position]	[Stakeholder group]	[E-mail]

DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any presentation used (ppt, pdf, etc.).• Several pictures of the event, even if the event is held online (screenshots) (jpg, pdf, etc.).• Any dissemination material produced for the event: poster, leaflet, etc. (jpg, pdf, etc.).• Any resulting publication (pdf, doc, etc.).• Any other documentation related to the event like the agenda, any working document, etc. (pdf, doc, etc.)
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	

6. Current state of NOVAFERT RWGs

By the time the RWGs were established, the number of members were:

- Belgium (Flanders): 15 members.
- Croatia (Continental Croatia): 15 members.
- Finland (South-West Finland): 8 members.
- Ireland (East Ireland): 10 members.
- Poland (South-East Poland): 12 members.
- Spain (Andalusia): 34 members.
- Spain (Catalonia): 44 members.

The current state of the NOVAFERT RWGs, in terms of number of members and meetings held, is summarised in the following subsections.

6.1. Belgium – Flanders

6.1.1. Core group

The members of the Flemish RWG core group are:

- Research centre.
- Farmer.
- Foundation.
- Research centre.
- Farmer.

6.1.2. RWG members

The Flemish RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 15 members, from which 12 belong to the private sector (5 are farmers, 4 to foundations, 2 to SMEs and 1 to a large company), 1 to the public sector (1 to the national public administration) and 2 to the academic sector (2 to research centres).

Figure 4. Composition of the Flemish RWG by November, 2023

6.1.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- June 14th, 2023 (3 attendees): meeting online with a professional organisation for farmers and landscapers to disseminate the project, ask them to be part of the RWG and compile some relevant information for the SWOT analysis.
- June 20th, 2023 (37 attendees): meeting held in Ghent, Belgium in the framework of the Nutricycle Vlaanderen platform (Nutro2Cycle project) event on the future sustainable farming in Flanders. The project was presented, and relevant regional information on main challenges and needs was compiled.
- June 21st, 2023 (4 attendees): meeting online with a research institute that is also active in the NOVAFERT sister project FER-PLAY to introduce NOVAFERT, ask

them to be part of the RWG, introduce the SWOT analysis methodology and compile some relevant information for completing it.

6.2. Croatia – Continental Croatia

6.2.1. Core group

The members of the Croatian RWG core group are:

- Farmer.
- Farmer and Business – SME.

6.2.2. RWG members

The Croatian RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 15 members, from which 10 belong to the private sector (3 are farmers, and 7 to SMEs), 4 to the academic sector (4 to universities) and 1 to the civil society (1 to an NGO).

Figure 5. Composition of the Croatian RWG by November, 2023

6.2.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- August 31st, 2023 (6 attendees): meeting held in Sisak, Croatia to introduce NOVAFERT, ask them to be part of the RWG, introduce the SWOT analysis methodology and compile some relevant information for completing it.

6.3. Finland – South-West Finland

6.3.1. Core group

The members of the Finish RWG core group are:

- Farmer.
- Business - Large company.
- National public administration.
- NGO.

6.3.2. RWG members

The Finish RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 8 members, from which 6 belong to the private sector (3 are farmers, and 3 to large companies), 1 to the public sector (1 to the national public administration) and 1 to the civil society (1 to an NGO).

Figure 6. Composition of the Finish RWG by November, 2023

6.3.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- June 20th, 2023 (7 attendees): meeting online with companies, ministerial advisers, farmers, etc. to disseminate the project, ask them to be part of the RWG and compile some relevant information for the SWOT analysis.
- Scheduled meeting for December 13th, 2023 (29 attendees are expected): meeting to be held in Vinkkilä, Finland to introduce NOVAFERT, ask the attendees to be part of the RWG and compile relevant info for the SWOT analysis.

6.4. Ireland – East Ireland

6.4.1. Core group

The members of the Irish RWG core group are:

- Research centre.
- Research centre.
- Research centre.
- Research centre.

6.4.2. RWG members

The Irish RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 10 members, from which 2 belong to the private sector (2 are farmers), 7 to the academic sector (7 to research centres) and 1 to the civil society (1 to an association).

Figure 7. Composition of the Irish RWG by November, 2023

6.4.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- November 10th, 2022 (26 attendees): meeting held in Wexford, Ireland to target people working within the industry giving agronomic advice and selling fertilisers to farmers, introduce the project and gather information on nutrient recovery technologies and products throughout the country.
- November 10th, 2022 (5 attendees): meeting held in Wexford, Ireland in the framework of a soil health open day part of a soil health conference, to promote the project and the RWG.
- March 20th, 2023 (4 attendees): meeting held in Down, Ireland with a company that refines broiler manure into a pelletised product to promote NOVAFERT and identify any areas where the project may be able support the business.
- April 25th, 2023 (8 attendees): meeting held in Wicklow, Ireland to welcome additional members to the group, introduce and update ongoing activities and visit two farmers which are using alternative fertilising products.

6.5. Poland – South-East Poland

6.5.1. Core group

The members of the Polish RWG core group are:

- National public administration.
- Business - SME.
- Research centre.

6.5.2. RWG members

The Polish RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 12 members, from which 3 belong to the private sector (2 are farmers and 1 to an SME), 4 to the public sector (1 to the national public administration and 3 to regional administrations), 3 to the academic sector (2 to universities and 1 to a research centre) and 2 to the civil society (2 to NGOs).

Figure 8. Composition of the Polish RWG by November, 2023

6.5.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- July 6th, 2023 (8 attendees): meeting online with companies, researchers, etc. to disseminate the project, ask them to be part of the RWG and compile some relevant information for the SWOT analysis.
- October 31st, 2023 (2 attendees): meeting online with a researcher. to introduce NOVAFERT and compile some relevant information for the SWOT analysis.

6.6. Spain – Andalusia

6.6.1. Core group

The members of the Andalusian RWG core group are:

- Business - Large company.
- Business - SME.
- Research centre.

6.6.2. RWG members

The Andalusian RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 34 members, from which 24 belong to the private sector (2 to foundations, 8 to SMEs and 14 to large companies), 1 to the public sector (1 to the local public administration) and 9 to the academic sector (2 to universities, 6 to research centres and 1 to a technological centre).

Figure 9. Composition of the Andalusian RWG by November, 2023

6.6.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- May 24th, 2023 (39 attendees): meeting held in Vélez-Málaga, Spain in the framework of NOVAFERT project and in collaboration with another Horizon Europe project, P2Green, also devoted to the use of secondary raw materials to produce fertilisers, in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area with stakeholders from the water management and regeneration sector, as well as from the agronomic sector. During this event, the attendees have been able to provide relevant information at regional level on the main challenges and needs they face, what has been used for the preparation of the SWOT analysis.
- June 20th, 2023 (6 attendees): meeting online with CETENMA, the coordinator of FER-PLAY, NOVAFERT's sister project. CETENMA is located in Murcia, a neighbourhood region of Andalusia sharing similar problems and challenges. Possible synergies and potential joint activities between projects in which CETENMA and BIOAZUL are involved. Furthermore, preliminary results of the SWOT analysis were shared and discussed.
- June 20th, 2023 (2 attendees): meeting online with CEBAS-CSIC facilitated by our national partner EIT Food focused on the use of reclaimed water in agriculture. Preliminary results of the SWOT were shared and discussed.
- June 28th, 2023 (6 attendees): meeting online with IMIDA, the regional neighbour Murcian Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development to share information about the project, the preliminary results of the SWOT and the upcoming RWGs activities.
- July 20th, 2023 (5 attendees): meeting held in Cartagena, Spain with CETENMA, the coordinator of FER-PLAY, NOVAFERT's sister project. Additional results of the SWOT analysis were shared and discussed, together with cross-fertilisation regional activities between FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT projects.

6.7. Spain – Catalonia

6.7.1. Core group

The members of the Catalan RWG core group are:

- Business - Large company.
- Technology centre.

- Regional public administration.
- Business – SME.
- Business – SME.
- Association.

6.7.2. RWG members

The Catalan RWG accounts until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) 42 members, from which 28 belong to the private sector (11 are farmers, 15 to SMEs and 2 to large companies), 9 to the public sector (9 to regional public administrations), 3 to the academic sector (2 to universities and 1 to a technological centre) and 2 to the civil society (2 to associations).

Figure 10. Composition of the Catalanian RWG by November, 2023

6.7.3. RWG meetings

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are summarised below (the fiches reporting these events are further attached as annexes):

- May 30th, 2023 (5 attendees): meeting online with the board of sustainable livestock management in the region, a fertilisers production company and private entrepreneurs in the areas of livestock and waste management to share information about the project and several upcoming activities, like the SWOT analysis preparation.
- June 16th, 2023 (3 attendees): meeting online with the ItaCyL group on Bio economy in the agrifood sector facilitated by our national partner EIT Food focused on the fertilising product resulting from the project LIFE Green Ammonia, their insights about the technology and the difficulties they have faced. Preliminary results of the SWOT were shared and discussed.
- June 19th, 2023 (2 attendees): meeting online with the Chemistry Department of ETSIAAB (UPM, Madrid) facilitated by our national partner EIT Food focused on the impacts of nitrogen fertilisation, specially related to GHG emissions.. Preliminary results of the SWOT were shared and discussed.
- October 18th, 2023 (49 attendees): meeting held in Vic, Spain in the framework PATT Conference on new bio fertiliser products recovered from livestock manure. The aim was to discuss about technical considerations and regulatory framework of biofertilisers made from nutrients recovered from livestock manure. The event brought together various actors interested in the valorisation of livestock manure to show some of the latest advances obtained in European projects underway in this field, as NOVAFERT and FERTIMANURE. During this event, preliminary results of the SWOT analysis were shared and discussed.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. Information and consent form template

Information and consent form for stakeholders to join the Regional Working Groups

1. Information about the project

NOVAFERT is a project funded by the EU, running from September 1st, 2022 until August 31st, 2025. It aims to demonstrate the technical, economic, and environmental feasibility and safe use of a wide portfolio of at least 25 alternative fertilising products, containing recovered nutrients from 6 different waste streams, with the goal of facilitating the replacement of synthetic and mineral fertilisers.

More info available at www.novafert.eu.

2. Regional Working Groups

You are invited to participate in the Regional Working Group (RWG) organised by [NAME OF THE PARTNER] in the framework of the NOVAFERT project. Please take the time to read this information letter carefully before you decide to take part in this activity. Do not hesitate to ask questions if there are any ambiguities or if you would need additional information. Once you have decided to participate, please sign the consent form on the last page.

2.1. What is the purpose of the Regional Working Groups?

The RWGs are aimed at engaging stakeholders from the NOVAFERT target regions and create a broader Community of Practice for the use of alternative fertilisers. The [NAME OF THE REGION] RWG will target the [INCLUDE THE MAIN SECONDARY MATERIALS], and it will be coordinated by [NAME OF THE PARTNER], which acts as regional representative of the NOVAFERT consortium.

The expected objectives and outcomes of the RWG are the following:

- Provide practical recommendations to develop Region Specific Action Plans.
- Be engaged in the implementation of alternative fertilising solutions.
- Seek opportunities to perform cooperative activities.
- Create a permanent cluster in the region to adopt and disseminate alternative fertilising products.

At least 4 meetings (face-to-face or online) will be organised for the RWG members. Furthermore, 3 participatory workshops will be organised in the region, being expected the participation of the RWG members, as well as of other relevant stakeholders of the region.

2.2. Participation in the Regional Working Group

Your participation in the RWG is completely voluntary and there can be no coercion in any way. You may withdraw from it at any time without having to provide a reason.

3. Information about Privacy and Personal Data

The legal framework for the processing of personal data and confidential information in the context of the Regional Working Group is defined by:

- The European General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 of April 27, 2016, in force since May 25, 2018 (the GDPR).
- [INCLUDE THE REFERENCE TO NATIONAL LAW PROTECTION DATA IN YOUR COUNTRY].

3.1. Which kind of data are collected?

The following main personal data will be processed:

- Name and surname.
- Position.
- Affiliation.
- E-mail address.
- Major sector/s of expertise.

Personal data will be collected via surveys, interviews, audio and video recordings of meetings and workshops.

3.2. Why are these personal data collected?

Your personal data will be used for the project purposes only, as described in the section above. Specifically, they will be used to facilitate the activities of the RWG and to inform you on the project updates.

They will also serve to identify the key experts at the different levels of the value chain which can provide their expertise and favour the knowledge exchange about the emerging opportunities, as well as the environmental and socio-economic impacts related to the use of locally or regionally available fertilising products recycled from raw materials.

3.3. What is the legal ground for processing personal data in the Regional Working Group?

For the processing of your personal data, your explicit permission will be asked via the 'consent form'. This consent can be withdrawn at any time by notifying the facilitator of your RWG, [NAME OF THE PARTNER].

3.4. Who has access to my (personal) data?

As facilitator of the RWG, [NAME OF THE PARTNER] will have access to your personal data with the purpose of organising the RWG activities. NOVAFERT project partners can also have access to your personal data for other project purposes (i.e., the preparation of deliverables or other kinds of reports). Data will be kept in the NOVAFERT protected SharePoint until the end of the project. Data will be treated in the strictest confidence, and information will not be reported or published in such a way that individual respondents can be identified.

3.5. Reuse of data

The collected data may also be useful and thus reused later for other research projects, by other researchers within Europe. To this end, all the necessary measures will be taken to guarantee the confidentiality of your personal data [TO BE DISCUSSED WITH OTHER PARTNERS].

3.6. What rights do you have as a participant with regards to the processing of your personal data?

In accordance with European and [INCLUDE THE REFERENCE TO YOUR COUNTRY LEGISLATION], your personal privacy is respected. As already indicated, you may withdraw your consent at any time without giving any reason. This means that your data will not be processed any further from the moment of withdrawal.

You have the right to consult the data which have been collected about you and you may also request a copy, as long as this does not violate the rights and freedoms of others. Any incorrect data about you can be corrected at your request. Moreover, you have the right to be forgotten; this means that, after withdrawing your permission, you can ask to have your personal data removed.

3.7. How can I file a complaint?

If you want to file a complaint about the way your personal data are handled or if you have any questions regarding your personal data, please contact [NAME OF THE RESPONSIBLE PERSON AT COUNTRY LEVEL] and/or Margherita Genua / Katrien Windels / Nimisha Edayilam.

CONSENT FORM

A. Consent for participation in the Regional Working Group

Please check the appropriate box	YES	NO
I voluntarily participate in the Regional Working Group and give permission to the facilitator to process, store, analyse and report on my data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I know that I may withdraw from the Regional Working Group at any time without giving a reason for this decision and without it affecting in any way my continued relationship with the facilitator.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have read the information sheet and have received sufficient explanation of the nature, purpose, duration, and expected outcomes of the project. I was given the opportunity to ask questions and I received satisfactory answers to all my questions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

B. Consent for the processing of personal data

Please check the appropriate box	YES	NO
I have read the information form and I know that I have rights to safeguard my privacy (including access, correction, deletion) and to whom I should turn to exercise these rights.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I give permission to the Regional Working Group facilitators and the NOVAFERT project partners to collect, process and store (personal) data from me for the purposes of the project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
[IF APPLICABLE] I give permission to be included recognisably in publications [BE SPECIFIC] as part of the project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C. Consent about the reuse and sharing of data

Please check the appropriate box	YES	NO
I give permission for my data to be reused for further research or follow up actions beyond the scope of the current project.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I give permission to share my data for further research or follow up actions. In doing so, all necessary measures will be taken to protect the confidentiality of my personal data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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Name of the participant:
Date:
Signature:

ANNEX 2. Lists of Regional Working Groups members (by November, 2023)

RWG members for Flanders region, Belgium

The members of the Flemish RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	Is the source of information related to any... ...EU project? ...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?	Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable)	Position	Location
Farmers	Private sector	Regional platform	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Farmer	Veldstraat 218, 9140 Temse
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	Fertimanure	EU project	Fertimanure	Farmer	Grote Stadenstraat 9, 8830 Hooglede
Farmers	Private sector	Regional platform	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Farmer	Sint-Amandsstraat, 8740 Pittem
Research centre	Private sector	Network of contacts	Inagro	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Researcher	Ghent, Rumbeke-Beitem, BELGIUM
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	DLV	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Director	
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	Boerenbond	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Director	Diestsevest 40, 3000 Leuven
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	Boerenbond	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Researcher	Diestsevest 40, 3000 Leuven

National public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Researcher	
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	ABS	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Director	
Research centre	Private sector	Network of contacts	VCM	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Researcher	
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Aquafin NV	EU project	Walnut	Researcher	Dijkstraat 8, 2630 Aartselaar
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Bio Sterco	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen		Grote Stadenstraat 9, 8830 Hooglede
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	IVACO	National project	BIODEN	Farmer	Gistel-Zevokote
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	NV De Zwanebloem	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Farmer	NV De Zwanebloem
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	Boerenbond	Regional project	Nutricycle Vlaanderen	Researcher	Diestsevest 40, 3000 Leuven

RWG members for Continental Croatia region

The members of the Croatian RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the	Is the source of information related to any... ...EU project? ...national project? ...regional	Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable)	Position	Location
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			stakeholder has been extracted	project? ...none of them?			
University	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Full time professor	Zagreb
University	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		full time professor in a permanent position	Zagreb
University	Academic sector	Regional operational group	Link	National project	The possibility of using digestate from the biogas plant as a fertiliser and soil improvement	professor	Križevci
University	Academic sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		professor	Osijek
NGO	Civil society	Network of contacts		Not applicable		director	Zagreb
Farmers	Civil society	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Sisak
Farmers	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Grubišno Polje
Farmers	Civil society	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Ježdovec

Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Grubišno Polje
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable			Vinkovci
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable			Zagreb
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Vrbovec
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable			Zagreb
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Zadar
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		director	Novi Marof

RWG members for South-West Finland region

The members of the Finish RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from	Is the source of information related to any... ...EU project?	Link / reference / name of the	Position	Location
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			which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?	project (if applicable)		
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			Vehmaa
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			Joutseno
Business - Large company	Private sector	National platform		Not applicable		director	Kanttua
Business - Large company	Private sector	National platform		Not applicable			Helsinki
National public administration	Public sector	National platform		Not applicable			Helsinki
NGO	Private sector	National platform		Not applicable			Helsinki
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			Lielhti
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			

RWG members for East Ireland region

The members of the Irish RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of	Is the source of information related to any...	Link / reference / name of the	Position	Location
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			the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	...EU project? ...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?	project (if applicable)		
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	EU project	https://www.nutri-know.eu/	Research officer	Wexford
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	EU project	https://www.nutri-2cycle.eu/	Research officer	Wexford
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	Not applicable		Senior research officer	Wexford
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	Not applicable		Specialist	Wexford
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	Not applicable		Specialist	Wicklow
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	Not applicable		Farmer	Wicklow
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	Not applicable		Farmer	Wicklow
Association	Civil society	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	EU project	https://www.nutri-know.eu/	Senior policy officer	Ireland

Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	National project	Low Farm N	Research student	Wexford
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to RWG organised by NOVAFERT	EU project	https://nutri-checknet.eu/events/	Research officer	Wexford

RWG members for South-East Poland region

The members of the Polish RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	Is the source of information related to any... ...EU project? ...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?	Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable)	Position	Location
National public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Expert	Bydgoszcz, Poland
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Co-founder & R&D Director	Kłobuck, Poland
NGO	Civil society	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Chairman of the board	Krakow, Poland
University	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		PhD student	Krakow, Poland

Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Research Assistant	Krakow, Poland
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Farmer	Olszyna, Poland
Regional public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Engineer	Lisów, Poland
University	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Research Assistant & Farmer	Krakow, Poland
Farmers	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Farmer	Tocholow, Poland
NGO	Civil society	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Volunteer	Miechow, Poland
Regional public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Manager	Ksiaz Wielki, Poland
Regional public administration	Public sector	Professional contacts via desk research		Not applicable		Head of the Environmental Protection Department	Rzeszów, Poland

RWG members for Andalusia region, Spain

The members of the Andalusian RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	Is the source of information related to any...	Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable)	Position	Location
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				...EU project? ...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?			
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Conputing engineer	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Intern	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Intern	Velez-Malaga

Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Auditor	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green		Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Agricultural engineer	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Consultant for food safety systems	Velez-Malaga

Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Agricultural technician	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	EU project	P2Green	Agricultural engineer	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in P2Green project	EU project	P2Green	Quality and food safety technician	Velez-Malaga
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in P2Green project	EU project	P2Green	Managing Board Member	Velez-Malaga
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in P2Green project	EU project	P2Green	Project Manager	Malaga
Foundation	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in P2Green project	EU project	P2Green	Manager	Malaga
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Manager	Torre del Mar

Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Executive board member	Torre del Mar
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Vice-president	Torre del Mar
Business - SME	Private sector	Other sectorial event	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	Not applicable		Co-founder and CEO	Caceres
Business - SME	Private sector	Other sectorial event	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2Green projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	Not applicable		Sales director	Caceres
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in P2Green project	EU project	P2Green	CEO	Velez-Malaga
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Technician	Algarrobo
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Senior Scientist	Algarrobo
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Research Professor	Algarrobo

Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Manager	Algarrobo
Local public administration	Public sector	Regional cluster	Collaboration in RichWater project	EU project	RichWater	Member	Algarrobo
Business - SME	Private sector	Professional contacts via desk research	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	Not applicable		CEO	Sevilla
Business - Large company	Private sector	Other sectorial event	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	Not applicable		Marketing manager	Cordoba
Business - Large company	Private sector	Other sectorial event	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/	Not applicable		Sustainability and biodiversity manager	Cordoba
Business - Large company	Private sector	Other sectorial event	Attendance to the regional event organised by NOVAFERT and P2GreeN projects in Vélez-	Not applicable			

			Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/				
University	Public sector	Network of contacts	BIOAZUL collaborator	EU project	UrBAN-WASTE	Project manager	Bologne
University	Public sector	Network of contacts	BIOAZUL collaborator	EU project	EIT-FOOD RIS Fellowships	Intern	Bologne
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Collaboration in TURaS project via Promalaga, a public-private company part of the Malaga City Council that works to encourage the creation of new companies by offering support, advice, training, subsidies and a network of 13 incubators https://www.promalaga.es/	EU project	TURaS	Chief Technical Officer	Malaga
Technology centre	Private sector	Network of contacts	Coordinators of FER-PLAY project, the sister project of NOVAFERT	EU project	FER-PLAY	Environmental Area R&D&I Responsible	Cartagena
Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	BIOAZUL collaborator	Not applicable		Technician of the Research Results Transfer Office (OTRI) for the Sustainability and Fruit and Vegetable Quality Team	La Alberca

Research centre	Public sector	Network of contacts	EIT Food member	Not applicable		Director - Manager	Seville
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RWG members for Catalonia region, Spain

The members of the Catalan RWG are until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project):

Type of stakeholder	Sector	Source of information	Link / reference / short description of the source from which the name of the stakeholder has been extracted	Is the source of information related to any... ...EU project? ...national project? ...regional project? ...none of them?	Link / reference / name of the project (if applicable)	Position	Location
Business - Large company	Private sector	Network of contacts	The Fertiliser company is located in a region near by and has a long history of collaboration with BETA tech center. For instance it is partner in other projects led by BETA such as Fertimanure, working on valorisation of manure	Not applicable		Fertiliser company investing in organic fertilisers	Aragón
Technology centre	Academic sector	Regional cluster	BETA collaborator as Head of transfer, business and territory	Not applicable			Vic

Regional public administration	Public sector	Regional cluster	Collaboration with the department in many projects, operational groups and regional activities	Not applicable		Regional Department of Climate Action	Lleida
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Belong to the network of contacts from Regional front runners regarding organic waste treatment	Not applicable		Only 10% of their feedstock is manure	Sant Bartomeu del Grau
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA, as many companies we work with requested us aid to help them in the decision making of the treatment of the digestate of the plant considering current legislation	Not applicable	www.sunchemicals.eu	Regulatory Specialist	Vic
Association	Civil society	Regional platform	Previous collaborations in Operational Groups from Catalonia	Not applicable	-		Barcelona
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts	Link made via Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Not applicable		Selected for Living Lab	Lleida
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Link made via Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Not applicable		Selected for living lab but not available for being part of the Regional Working group	Navas
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts	Link made via Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Not applicable		Part of the same consortia than Consortium	Viver I Serrateix -

						Genia Bioenergy	
Farmers	Civil society	Network of contacts	Link made via transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	National project	BIOFERTI+	Santa Cecilia de Voltrega
Farmers	Civil society	Regional platform	Link made via transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Link made via the transfer, business and territory unit from BETA	Not applicable	https://gapcooperativa.com/ GAP Cooperativa, as a farmers organisation, had to deal with the excess of nitrogen present on their pigs manure. Their solution was to gather together and invest on the construction of a biogas plant, owned by the then created TRACJUSA SA. They built this 100.000 Tn/year treatment capacity plant which has been running since its creation.	Lleida
Association	Civil society	Regional cluster			Not applicable		

Farmers	Public sector	Regional cluster		Not applicable	Innovi Home		
Business - SME	Civil society	Regional cluster		Not applicable			
Business - SME	Civil society	Regional cluster		Not applicable	https://advecologica.org/es/sobre-ladv/		Lleida
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Vila Sana anaerobic digestion plant, they produce ammonium sulfate and solar drying of the solid fraction of the digestate	Vilansana
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable	Quienes somos Labin nutrición vegetal	Production of organic fertilisers	
Farmers	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		manure valorisation	
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			

Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Solid fraction of manure	
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Business - SME	Private sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		Slaughterhouse	
Business - Large company	Private sector	Conference		Not applicable			
Farmers	Civil society	Regional platform		Not applicable	https://uniopagos.cat/qui-som/referents-al-camp-catala/		
Regional public administration	Public sector	Regional platform		Not applicable			
Regional public administration	Public sector	Regional platform		Not applicable	https://residus.gencat.cat/ca/inici		
Farmers	Civil society	Regional platform		Not applicable			
University	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Regional public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Farmers	Civil society	Network of contacts		Not applicable			
Regional public administration	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable			

Farmers	Unió de Pagèsos	Civil society	Regional platform		Not applicable		
Regional public administration	Agència Catalana de l'Aigua	Public sector	Regional platform		Not applicable		
Regional public administration	Agència Catalana de Residus	Public sector	Regional platform		Not applicable		
Farmers	Clúster Maquinaria agrícola FEMAC	Civil society	Regional platform		Not applicable		
University	Escola agrària Manresa	Academic sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		
Regional public administration	Incavi (Institut català de la vinya i el vi)	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		
Farmers	la Vinyeta	Civil society	Network of contacts		Not applicable		
Regional public administration	ADRINOC - Associació Per Al Desenvolupament Rural Integral De La Zona Nord-Oriental De Catalunya. Grup d'Acció Local LEADER	Public sector	Network of contacts		Not applicable		
	Espigall						

ANNEX 3. Fiches of the Regional Working Groups meetings held (by November, 2023)

RWG meetings for Flanders region, Belgium

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

FLEMISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting Flanders region		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	[14/06/2023 – 9.00-9.30-Online]		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Nimisha Edayilam – UGent		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	BoerenBond	Consultant Circular Economy	Farmers' Union
	BoerenBond	Entrepreneurship & Innovation	Farmers' Union
	UGent	NOVAFERT Coordinator	University
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>The Boerenbond is a professional organisation for farmers and landscapers in Flanders and East Belgium. They focus on advocacy, training, networking, innovation, and providing support and guidance.</p> <p>The meeting was held online, with the facilitator (Nimisha Edayilam) of the regional working group providing an introduction to the NOVAFERT project, the regional group members' expectations, and an introduction to the SWOT analysis</p>		

	methodology previously created for the NOVAFERT project. The participants discussed about the next steps and provided preliminary information for completing a SWOT analysis.
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• PPT shared with the participants.• Report of attendance from Teams.
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	Homepagina Boerenbond
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use the results of the activities to define the attributes of the NOVAFERT SWOT for the Flanders area.• Share the SWOT draft with the RWG members and ask for feedback and input.

FLEMISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	1 st RWG physical meeting in the Flanders region
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/06/2023 – Ghent, Belgium

FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Maarten De Coninck+ Erik Meers – UGent	
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	VLM	Research
	VCM	Research
	INNOLAB	Research
	Danis NV	Agriculture
	Nutriproces bv	Agriculture
	ILVO	Research
	Smart Renure	Agriculture
	Geen	Agriculture
	Vanhove	Agriculture
	Inagro	Research
	Weet niet wat u hiermee bedoeld	Agriculture
	green tile	Agriculture
	NAC	Agriculture

	NAC	Agriculture
	Bodemkundige Dienst van België	Research
	bedrijfsleider	Agriculture
	Vanhove	Agriculture
	Danis	Agriculture
	B2BE Facilitator	Agriculture
	ILVO	Research
	nv Leievoeders	Industry
	Landbouwbedrijf	Agriculture
	ABS	Agriculture
	De Coen	Agriculture
	Abs	Agriculture
	Inagro	Research
	Boer Burger Belangen, Ik ben zeer geïnteresseerd maar kan niet aanwezig zijn.	

	Mogelijk om achteraf documentatie te verkrijgen of wordt deze misschien ook gelifestreamd? Mvg, Tine	
	Stam Agro	
	agra	Agriculture
	ABS	Agriculture
	Suin bv	Agriculture
	landbouw en visserij abco	
	agro-experten	Agriculture
	Clarebout Geert BV	Agriculture
	Landbouw	Agriculture
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	Nutricycle Vlaanderen is a platform that already exists in Flanders as part of another Horizon Europe Project, Nutri2Cycle. As Nutri2Cycle comes to an end in September, this platform will continue running in the framework of NOVAFERT with RWG activities. Nutricycle Vlaanderen organised an event on the future of sustainable farming in Flanders on June 20, 2023. Farmers, policymakers, and farming and environmental organisations all had a chance to share their perspectives on the subject. The participation list also includes potential members who wish to continue actively	

	<p>participating in NOVAFERT's RWG operations. The meeting discussed the NOVAFERT project and its activities.</p> <p>During this event, they have been able to provide relevant information at regional level on the main challenges and needs they face.</p> <p>This will be the first of many local meetings and collaborative activities organised by UGent, with the possibility of sharing with other projects such as Fertimanure and Nutri2cycle.</p>
<p>ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED</p>	
<p>LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE</p>	<p>Home - Nutricycle</p>

ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible follow-up meeting to discuss the attributes of the NOVAFERT SWOT for the Flanders region and determine their relevance. • Share the SWOT draft with the RWG members and ask them for comments / validation.

FLEMISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	3 rd RWG meeting Flanders region		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	[21/06/2023 – 15.00-15.45-Online]		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Nimisha Edayilam – UGent		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Heirbaut Hoeveproducten	Farm	Farmer
	Inagro	Research institute	Practical researcher energy and circular economy
	Inagro	Research institute	Researcher
	UGent	NOVAFERT Coordinator	University

DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES

The meeting was held online, with the facilitator (Nimisha Edayilam) of the regional working group introducing the NOVAFERT project, the regional group members' expectations, and an introduction to the SWOT analysis methodology previously created for the NOVAFERT project. The participants discussed about the next steps and provided preliminary information for completing a SWOT analysis.

Inagro is a research institute that is also active in the NOVAFERT sister project FER-PLAY, participants addressed the possibility of partnering in RWG activities.

Kris Heirbaut is an experienced farmer who explained the Threads/challenges in the use of innovative fertilisers produced from secondary raw materials based on his own experiences. Those points have been noted.

Oversupply of sustainability programmes: entrenched interests try to introduce their own form of sustainability or green washing; farmers are over-inquired for such initiatives.

Eco schemes, multi-variety crops, and even the reintroduction of seeds from extremely old species are not compatible with modern sustainable fertilisers.

The overflow of evolving rules and new information and conditions, as well as a rising diversity of potentially fascinating cultivations and all data a farmer must analyse, complicate matters, and farmers may be afraid of this complexity; new fertilising technologies may even complicate matters further.

ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED

- PPT shared with the participants.
- Report of attendance from Teams.

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	<p>www.inagro.be</p> <p>Heirbaut Hoeveproducten</p>
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the results of the activities to define the attributes of the NOVAFERT SWOT for the Flanders area. • Share the SWOT draft with the RWG members and ask for feedback and input.

RWG meetings for Continental Croatia region

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

CONTINENTAL CROATIA REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	31/ 08/ 2023 – Sisak, (Croatia)
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	IPS Konzalting

PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	IPS Konzalting	Project manager and director at IPS Konzalting	Business - SME – private sector
	IPS Konzalting	Senior consultant	Business - SME – private sector
	IPS Konzalting	Project assistant	Business - SME – private sector
	IPS Konzalting	Project assistant	Business - SME – private sector
	IPS Konzalting	Project assistant	Business - SME – private sector
	IPS Konzalting	Procjet assistant	Business - SME – private sector
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>The meeting was held face to face at IPS Konzalting, Sisak, Croatia. The NOVAFERT project is briefly presented, as well as goals and project activities. Furthermore, activities related to the SWOT analysis were presented. After the introduction, potential strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to the alternative fertilisers were presented. Members of RWG discussed and scored the statements related to three second raw materials (animal manure, digestate, and bio-waste) in Continental Croatia.</p>		

<p>ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED</p>	
<p>LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.</p>	
<p>NEXT STEPS (if any)</p>	<p>The next step is organisation of the second meeting where other stakeholders will be involved (farmers, fertiliser producers). Additionally, after compiling the SWOT analyses and completing the related deliverable, the results will be presented to the RWG.</p>

RWG meetings for South-West Finland region

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

<p>FINISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING</p>	
<p>EVENT</p>	<p>1st RWG</p>

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/06/2023 – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Kari Ylivainio - Natural Resources Institute Finland]		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Ministry of Agriculture and Firestry	Ministerial adviser	Public
	Biolan Ltd	Director R&D and business development	Private
	ProAgria	Development director	NGO
	Biopir Ltd	Chairman of the Board	Private
	Farmers association (MTK)	Environmental expert	NGO
	Natural Resources Institute Finland	Senior researcher	Public
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>This was the first RWG meeting in Finland. Participant of RWG includes expertise from the following areas related to alternative fertilisers: legislation, production, agronomic efficiency and safe use from the environmental point of view. Also knowledge about farmer’s acceptance of alternative fertilisers is well presented in RWG.</p> <p>Short introduction round was conducted at the beginning of the meeting followed by the introduction of NOVAFERT project and SWOT analyses that will be conducted for the alternative</p>		

	fertilisers. After introduction of the SWOT analyses, potential strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threat related to the alternative fertilisers were presented and vivid discussions took place around these issues. Luke will collect the presented attributes into an excel file and will send it to RWG members for scoring the attributes within each matrix.
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	After compiling SWOT analyses and finalising the related deliverable, results will be presented for the RWG.

RWG meetings for East Ireland region

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

IRISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	10/11/2022, Johnstown Castle Co. Wexford, Ireland		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Dónal Kinsella – Teagasc		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Teagasc	Advisor	Public
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Enva	Waste management	Private
	Enva	Waste management	Private
	Teagasc		Public
	Teagasc	Teacher	Public
	Self employed	Farmer	Private
	Drummonds ltd	Advisor/sales	Private
	Grassland Agro	Product management	Private

	Grassland Agro	Advisor/sales	Private
	Grassland Agro	Advisor/sales	Private
	Grassland Agro	Advisor/sales	Private
	Grassland Agro	Advisor/sales	Private
	D.walsh+sons	Advisor/sales	Private
	Tirlán	Ruminant nutritionist	Civil
	Teagasc	Laboratory service	Public
	UCD	Lecturer	Academic
	Brett brothers ltd	Advisor/sales	Private
	Veolia	nutrient management	Private
	Teagasc	Phd student	Academic
	Teagasc	Field technician	Public
	Teagasc		Public
	Teagasc	Field technician	Public

	Teagasc	Phd student	Academic
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>Teagasc created a core group with colleagues within the organisation to organise our first workshop. The aim of the workshop was to target people working within the industry giving agronomic advice and selling fertiliser to farmers. The main purpose of this workshop was to introduce the NOVAFERT project and explain the role Teagasc had within the project. Teagasc is responsible for leading WP1 which involved getting as much information as possible on nutrient recovery technologies and products throughout the country. We took this opportunity to receive feedback from the group on nutrient recovery technologies and products that they have come across or seen farmers using within their role. We completed this task by facilitating small breakout sessions.</p>		
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ppt shared with the participants. • Sign in sheet. • Agenda. • Pictures of event. 		

Novafert

<p>LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.</p>	
<p>NEXT STEPS (if any)</p>	

IRISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	2 nd RWG meeting

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	10/11/2022, Johnstown Castle Co. Wexford, Ireland		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Dónal Kinsella – Teagasc		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public
	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>The 2nd regional working group meeting involved attending a soil health open day which was part of a soil health conference in which Teagasc organised. The target audience for this event was a broad range of stakeholders interested in the area of soil health, nutrient use efficiency, sustainability etc. We took this opportunity to introduce the work of NOVAFERT and promote the project to anyone attending the event. We had a display of alternative fertilisers for attendees to observe and also shared results from a five-year grassland trial being ran by Teagasc using alternative fertiliser sources.</p>		
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Board presentation. • Pictures. 		

Novafert

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.

https://youtu.be/a_dcVjJA0NI

NEXT STEPS (if any)

IRISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EVENT	3 rd RWG meeting		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/03/2023 Newry, Co. Down, Ireland		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Donal Kinsella		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public
	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public
	Private company	Company director	Private
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>Some members of the core RWG participated in the 3rd RWG meeting. The purpose of the 3rd RWG meeting was to go and meet with a company which is refining broiler manure into a pelletised product. This was an important aspect of our RWG establishment as we needed to get exposure to private industry within this field. The meeting consisted of interaction discussions regarding to nutrient recycling and a tour of their facilities. It was important to promote NOVAFERT at this meeting to identify any areas where the project may be able support the business.</p>		
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictures. 		

Novafert

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	

IRISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	4 th RWG meeting		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	25/04/2023 Arklow, Co. Wicklow, Ireland		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Donal Kinsella Teagasc		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Private company	Farmer	Private
	Private company	Farmer	Private
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public

	Teagasc	Researcher	Public/Academic
	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public/civil
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
	Teagasc	Advisor/specialist	Public/civil
	Teagasc	Researcher	Public
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	The purpose of our 4 th RWG was to welcome additional members to the group. The meeting consisted of introducing and updating ongoing activities within NOVAFERT and visit two farmers which are using alternative fertilising products.		
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictures. • Agenda. 		
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.			
NEXT STEPS (if any)			

RWG meetings for South-East Poland region

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

POLISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	06/07/2023, Online, 16.00-17.30 CET		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Marzena Smol – Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Polish Waterworks Chamber of Commerce / EurEua	Expert	National public organisation
	GreenBack Ltd.	Co-founder & R&D Director	Business – Small and sized enterprise (SME) Entrepreneur
	Optimus Foundation	Chairman of the board	Non-governmental organisation (NGO)
	AGH University of Science and Technology	PhD candidate	University

	Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences	Research Assistant	Research centre
	Herby Water Treatment Plant – Lisów Wastewater Treatment Plant	Engineer	Regional public administration
	Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences	Head of Division of Biogenic Raw Materials, Associate Professor, Coordinator of NOVAFERT project in Poland	Research centre
	Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences	Research Assistant, Coordinator of the RWG in Poland	Research centre
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>This was the inaugural Regional Working Group (RWG) gathering held in Poland. The meeting occurred virtually, bringing together participants from the Quadruple Helix, which encompasses representatives from the private, public, social, and civil sectors.</p> <p>At the onset of the meeting, the RWG members introduced themselves. Subsequently, the primary objectives and underlying principles of the NOVAFERT project were outlined. Examples of alternative fertiliser sources being investigated within the project were also presented. After this initial introduction, the methodology for conducting SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis was presented. Subsequently, various strengths, weaknesses, opportunities,</p>		

	<p>and threats regarding the use of alternative fertilisers derived from animal manure, digestate, and sewage sludge were presented. Engaging discussions ensued on these topics.</p> <p>MEERI compiled the attributes that were presented into an Excel file, which was then shared with RWG members for review and the addition of supplementary matrix attributes.</p>
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presentation used (ppt).• Several pictures of the event (screenshots) (png).• Report of attendance from Webex (xlsx).• Agenda (pdf).
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Review and the addition of supplementary matrix attributes by RWG members.• Matrix attribute scoring.

POLISH REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	2 nd RWG meeting

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	31/10/2023, Online, 15.00-16.00 CET		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Paulina Marcinek – Mineral and Energy Economy Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	AGH University of Kraków, Poland	Research Assistant & Farmer	University
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>This constituted the 2nd gathering of the Regional Working Group (RWG) held in Poland. The meeting took place virtually and was attended by MSc Paulina Marcinek, the leader of the RWG in Poland, and MSc Paulina Oczkowicz, who serves as a research assistant at AGH University in Krakow and is also an active farmer.</p> <p>In the initial part of the meeting, the primary objectives and activities within the NOVAFERT project were introduced. Examples of alternative fertiliser sources being investigated within the project were also presented. Following the introduction, the SWOT methodology was explained, and data collected from the previous RWG meeting were presented and discussed.</p> <p>Finally, the actions to be undertaken within the RWG were presented.</p>		
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presentation used (ppt).• Several pictures of the event (screenshots) (png).• Report of attendance from Webex (xlsx).• Agenda (pdf).		

<p>LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.</p>	
<p>NEXT STEPS (if any)</p>	

RWG meetings for Andalusia region, Spain

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

ANDALUSIAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting in the Andalusian region

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	24/05/2023 – Vélez-Málaga (Spain)		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Pilar Zapata + Gerardo González – BIOAZUL		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	TROPS	Computer engineer	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Intern	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Intern	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Auditor	Business-Large company
	TROPS		Business-Large company
	TROPS	Agricultural engineer	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Consultant for food safety systems	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Agricultural technician	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Agricultural engineer	Business-Large company
	TROPS	Quality and food safety technician	Business-Large company

	TROPS	Managing Board Member	Business-Large company
	CETAQUA	Project Manager	Foundation
	CETAQUA	Manager	Foundation
	AXARAGUA	Manager	Business - SME
	AXARAGUA	Executive board member	Business - SME
	AXARAGUA	Vice-president	Business - SME
	Ergofito Iberica	Co-founder and CEO	Business - SME
	Ergofito Iberica	Sales director	Business - SME
	AgriSmart data	CEO	Business - SME
	IHSM-La Mayora	Field Technician	Research centre
	IHSM-La Mayora	Senior Scientist	Research centre
	IHSM-La Mayora	Research Professor	Research centre
	IHSM-La Mayora	Manager	Research centre
	Algarrobo Irrigation Community	Member	

	REALIMA Environmental Engineering	CEO	Business - SME
	Agbar Agriculture	Marketing manager	Business - Large company
	Agbar Agriculture	Sustainability and Biodiversity manager	Business - Large company
	Agbar Veolia Spain		Business - Large company
	BIOAZUL	CEO	Business - SME
	BIOAZUL	Marketing and communications Director	Business - SME
	BIOAZUL	Senior Project manager	Business - SME
	BIOAZUL	Project manager	Business - SME
	BIOAZUL	Senior Project manager	Business - SME
	BIOAZUL	Project manager	University
	BIOAZUL	Intern	University
	INNOVA IRV	Chief Technical Officer	Business - SME

DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES

Last May 24th, 2023, a regional event took place in the framework of NOVAFERT project and in collaboration with another Horizon Europe project, [P2Green](#), also devoted to the use of secondary raw materials to produce fertilisers, in Vélez-Málaga, Axarquía area, within the Andalusian region. This event, that constitutes the first NOVAFERT Regional Working Group (RWG) meeting, was organised by [BIOAZUL](#) in collaboration with other regional P2Green partners: [Trops](#), the first transnational producers organisation of Andalusia, specialised in the production and marketing of avocado and mango; [Cetaqua](#), a public-private water technology centre with headquarters in four different locations, one of them Andalusia; [Axaragua](#), the water management company of the of the Costa del Sol – Axarquía region; and [AgriSmart Data](#), a company devoted to smart farming.

The event counted with 39 attendees belonging, on the one hand, to the water management and regeneration sector, and, on the other hand, to the agronomic sector. During this event, they have been able to provide relevant information at regional level on the main challenges and needs they face.

The information gathered will be useful to perform the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threatens) analysis on the use of fertilisers produced using wastewater and sewage sludge as secondary raw materials, and very specially on the use or reclaimed water as alternative fertiliser.

The event counted with several presentations and activities:

- P2Green project: Transforming urban wastewater and organic solid waste into fertilisers. Miguel Angel Diaz. Project manager, Water resources management (CETAQUA).
- Lecture: "The future of the subtropical crops in the Axarquía region in a context of climate change". Iñaki Hormaza. Research Professor of the Subtropical and Mediterranean Fruit Growing Department (CSIC-IHSM "La Mayora").

- NOVAFERT Project: Development of innovative procedures and sustainable guidelines to promote the use of alternative fertilisers. Pilar Zapata. Senior manager of R+D+i projects (BIOAZUL S.L.).
- Interactive activities with stakeholders (1): identification of challenges, needs and benefits.
- Interactive activities with stakeholders (2): classification by relevance.
- Interactive activities with stakeholders (3): “in/out” activity.
- Interactive activities with stakeholders (4): stakeholders cooperation mapping.

This will be the first of several meetings and collaborative activities of the region that BIOAZUL will organise, when possible also sharing forces with other related projects like P2GreeN and/or [BONEX](#).

ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO
BE INCLUDED

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.

<https://www.NOVAFERT.eu/the-first-regional-working-group-organised-in-andalusia/>.

<https://www.cetaqua.com/p2green-agua-regenerada-axarquia/>.

<https://www.industriambiente.com/noticias/20230530/p2green-el-proyecto-europeo-que-pretende-validar-el-potencial-uso-del-agua-regenerada-como-biofertilizante-para-el-riego-en-la-axarquia-malaga>.

https://www.5aldia.org/key/noticias-de-socios-2023/trops-celebra-el-workshop-reducir--reutilizar-y-recuperar--organizado-dentro-del-proyecto-p2green_13453_1672_17528_0_1_in.html.

	<p>https://www.interempresas.net/Horticola/Articulos/482342-P2Green-proyecto-europeo-pretende-validar-potencial-uso-agua-regenerada-biofertilizante.html.</p> <p>https://www.retema.es/actualidad/p2green-un-proyecto-europeo-para-generar-biofertilizantes-partir-de-aguas-residuales.</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/trops_p2green-aguaregenerada-ihsmlamayora-activity-7067164865387192320-gOsp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop.</p> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cetaqua_sectoragraedcola-aguaregenerada-agricultura-activity-7069309951709437953-pCJB?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/PilarZapataAran/status/1661277952938524674?cxt=HHwWhIC2oeLfhY4uAAA A.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/bioazul_spain/status/1661272808461148160?cxt=HHwWglC99ai0g44uAAAA.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/fTROPS/status/1661284121920909316?cxt=HHwWiMC94ezGil4uAAAA.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/1661272807211257856?cxt=HHwWgMC-zZ-0g44uAAAA.</p>
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<p>Use the outcomes of the activities performed to define the attributes of the NOVAFERT SWOT for the Andalusia region and determine their relevance.</p> <p>Share the SWOT draft with the RWG members and ask them for comments / validation.</p>

ANDALUSIAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	Meeting to enlarge the RWG

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/06/2023 – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Pilar Zapata – BIOAZUL		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	R&D&I Project Coordinator – FER-PLAY project coordinator	Technology centre
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	Responsible for the European Projects Office	Technology centre
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	Environmental Area R&D&I Responsible	Technology centre
	BIOAZUL S.L.	Senior Project Manager	SME
	BIOAZUL S.L.	Project Manager	SME
	BIOAZUL S.L.	Senior Project Manager	SME
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	The meeting was devoted to discussing possible synergies and potential joint activities between projects in which CETENMA and BIOAZUL are involved, concretely:		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT.• HOOP, CETENMA's H2020 project.• VALUEWASTE, CETENMA's H2020 project.• P2GreeN, BIOAZUL's Horizon Europe project.• BONEX, BIOAZUL's PRIMA project. <p>The main idea was sharing the kind of documentation produced within each project and the upcoming events of each of them in which any of the other projects could collaborate.</p> <p>In this sense, one of the events mentioned was the next General Assembly of FER-PLAY project, which will take place in October 2023 in Murcia, Spain, and they are planning to organise an open day for other projects to be presented and perform any specific activity, if suitable.</p> <p>In addition, the NOVAFERT SWOT analysis was introduced to CETENMA staff and an initial discussion was held.</p>
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	

NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presential meeting to be organised next month in Cartagena, Murcia, where the discussion about the SWOT attributes will be resumed, and they will be also pondered to create the spider diagrams.
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ANDALUSIAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	Meeting to enlarge the RWG and identify attributes for the SWOT analysis		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/06/2023 – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Carmen Galindo – EIT Food		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	CEBAS-CSIC	Senior Scientist	Research and Technology Organisation (RTO)
	EIT Food	Key Account Manager	Research and Technology Organisation (RTO)
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p><i>Francisco Pedrero works at CEBAS-CSIC in Murcia (Spain), in the department of Irrigation, with a strong focus on precision agriculture (irrigation scheduling, sensing technology, deficit irrigation and optimisation on the use of alternative water sources, including reclaimed water, desalinated water.</i></p> <p>Order of the day:</p>		

- (EIT Food & CEBAS CSIC) Presentation round about CEBAS CSIC and EIT Food.
- (EIT Food) Introduction of NOVAFERT project & scope of the meeting.
- (CEBAS CSIC) Experience on the use / development / study of alternative fertilising products.
- (EIT Food & CEBAS CSIC) Identification of SWOT attributes for agreed waste streams – wastewater, sludge, animal manure, digestate, biowaste, organic by-products.

Minutes:

Conversation focusing on the use of reclaimed water in agriculture given his specialisation; some experience with sludge but not discussed.

Context: Murcia is very advanced in the use of reclaimed water in agriculture. As a starting point, the wastewater treatment technology in place in the region is one of the most advanced.

Strengths

- Potential to reduce the need of external inputs. Depending on the source of wastewater and type of treatment, a farmer can save 10 – 30% of N and P; and in some occasions higher amounts of K as this nutrient is almost not removed in the treatment process (not dangerous to environment).
- Stable water source – A minimum amount is always available as it is fed from wastewater treatment plants.

Weaknesses

- Full potential of reclaimed water (access to water source, recovery of nutrients and saving on agricultural inputs) is only attained applying good practices. This requires continuous

measurement of water composition, in order to adjust other parameters (pH, EC, nutrients) and fertilisation. Nowadays, accurate sensing technology is not accessible for everyone.

- Need to educate users (farmers) for a good management of this resource...Potential blockage of some nutrients due to incompatibilities between the fertilising plan & reclaimed water composition.
- Nutritional requirements of the crops vary over the cropping period, depending on the phenological stage; reclaimed water shall be used in combination with other water sources in order to balance the requirements.
- Depending on the wastewater treatment process, some of the water obtained can have very reduced amount of nutrients.
- Concerns on water's EC and pH levels.
- Composition of the reclaimed water varies with water sources, therefore an annual characterisation is needed.

Opportunities

- A lot of scientific work has been done in the past decades on the subject; regulations set a framework to increase the safety perception of this resource.
- Potential environmental benefits taking into consideration LCA – avoidance of the release of excess of nutrients.

Threads

- European regulation highly restrictive, might limit the adoption by some growers as they do not have the capacity to invest nor manage the tertiary treatment (if not assumed by the wastewater plants, or other parties) and /or might affect the prize of the water. Regulation

	<p>should focus not on the water arriving to the farm, but on the quality of the water used for irrigation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Double standards for different water sources (i.e., river flows, groundwater, reclaimed water) can limit the adoption of reclaimed water in agriculture, as it might be easier to use other sources (when available).
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Transfer data to relevant NOVAFERT partners.• Make intros between Pilar Zapata (Bioazul) and Francisco (CEBAS) to explore the collaboration within the RWG.

ANDALUSIAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	Meeting to enlarge the RWG

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	28/06/2023 – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Pilar Zapata – BIOAZUL		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	IMIDA, Murcian Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development	Technician of the Research Results Transfer Office (OTRI) for the Sustainability and Fruit and Vegetable Quality Team	Research centre
	IMIDA, Murcian Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development	Researcher and Coordinator of the Sustainability and Fruit and Vegetable Quality Team	Research centre
	IMIDA, Murcian Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development	Researcher and Coordinator of the Sustainability and Fruit and Vegetable Quality Team	Research centre
	IMIDA, Murcian Institute for Agricultural and Environmental Research and Development	Researcher of the Sustainability and Fruit and Vegetable Quality Team	Research centre
	BIOAZUL S.L.	Senior Project Manager	SME
	BIOAZUL S.L.	CEO and R&D&I Director	SME

DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>The meeting was devoted to introduce NOVAFERT project, explain the main outcomes expected and the potential activities in which they could collaborate and enlarge the RWG with the participation of this relevant research centre from the neighbouring Murcian region.</p> <p>In addition, possible synergies and potential joint actions in our respective regions, Andalusia and Murcia, were also discussed.</p> <p>In addition, the NOVAFERT SWOT analysis under development was introduced to IMIDA to check their opinion on the attributes identified up to that moment and ask for potential new ones.</p>
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<p>Presential meeting to be organised in Murcia, where the discussion about the SWOT attributes will continue.</p>

ANDALUSIAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING	
EVENT	Meeting to check potential collaborations with RWG members

DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	20/07/2023 – Cartagena, Murcia (Spain)		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Antonia Lorenzo – BIOAZUL		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	BIOAZUL S.L.	CEO and R&D&I Director	SME
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	Director	Technology centre
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	R&D&I Project Coordinator – FER-PLAY project coordinator	Technology centre
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	Responsible for the European Projects Office	Technology centre
	CETENMA, Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment	Environmental Area R&D&I Responsible	Technology centre

<p>DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES</p>	<p>The meeting was devoted to continue the discussion initiated with the previous online meeting, sharing the attributes identified for the NOVAFERT project and discussing about them.</p> <p>Joint potential future activities were also discussed; in this sense, CETENMA invited BIOAZUL to participate in the open session of their upcoming FER-PLAY annual meeting, that is intended to take place in October, 18th-20th, 2023. In addition, they suggested us to get in touch with the FER-PLAY project partner in charge of managing the stakeholder engagement activities. CETENMA will put us in touch to organise a meeting.</p> <p>Furthermore, CETENMA has asked BIOAZUL to become member of the External Advisory Board (EAB) for FER-PLAY project.</p>
<p>ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED</p>	
<p>LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.</p>	
<p>NEXT STEPS (if any)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare the collaboration for the open session of the next FER-PLAY annual meeting in Cartagena, Murcia. • Organisation of a meeting between FER-PLAY partner in charge of stakeholders engagement and BIOAZUL.

- Formalisation of the participation of BIOAZUL in the EAB of FER-PLAY.

RWG meetings for Catalonia region, Spain

The meetings held until November 2023 (the RWG will continue growing until the end of the project) are reported in the following fiches:

CATALAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	1 st RWG meeting Catalan Region		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	30/05/2023 – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Ana Robles Aguilar – BETA Tech Center		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	Sunchemicals	Director	Industry Regulation advisor
	Fertinagro – Grupo Tervalis	Head of department	Industry fertiliser company
	FCAC	Livestock waste management area	Public sector

	Board for the Sustainable management of livestock in Osona	Coordinator	Public Sector
	BETA Tech Center	Coordinator of the RWG	University
<p>DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES</p>	<p>The regional working group from Catalunya has been established and held its inaugural meeting on May 30th, 2023. The working group comprises members from the quadruple helix, encompassing universities, representatives from the social sector (such as farmer associations and the board of sustainable livestock management in the region) as well as members from a private fertilizer industry, the regional government, consultancies specialising in fertiliser regulation, and private entrepreneurs in the areas of livestock and waste management.</p> <p>The meeting took place online, and the BETA Center, the facilitator of the regional working group, provided an introduction to the NOVAFERT project. The participants discussed the future steps and expectations of the regional group members, and shared preliminary information necessary for conducting a SWOT analysis.</p> <p>The next meeting will be hold before the summer break and our first regional workshop will be organised in November.</p>		
<p>ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ppt shared with the participants. • Report of attendance from Teams. <p>Photo of the RWG facilitator while the online meeting</p>		

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.

Ferrán shared his other affiliation: www.bioregulatory.net

NEXT STEPS (if any)

CATALAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	Personal interview		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	16/06/2023 – 13.00 CEST – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Carmen Galindo – EIT Food		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	ItaCyL	Researcher	RTO
	ItaCyL	Researcher	RTO
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>ItaCyL group on Bio economy in the agrifood sector (<i>Grupo de Investigación en Residuos Ganaderos y de la Industria Alimentaria</i>) has developed a fertilising product in the framework of the project LIFE Green Ammonia, and would like to contribute with insights about the technology and the difficulties they have seen.</p> <p>Order of the day:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• (EIT Food & ItaCyL) Presentation round about ItaCyL and EIT Food.• (EIT Food) Introduction of NOVAFERT project & scope of the meeting.• (ItaCyL) Experience on the use / development of alternative fertilising products.• (EIT Food & ItaCyL) Identification of SWOT attributes for agreed waste streams – wastewater, sludge, animal manure, digestate, biowaste, organic by-products.		

Minutes:

Projects related to NOVAFERT in which ITACYL's group working on valorisation of livestock residues is working:

- Live Green Ammonia: <https://www.lifegreenammonia.eu/> → In this project they worked with membrane technology to extract ammonia from digestate and slurry. They treat it to get ammonium sulphate. Originally their intention was not to produce fertilisers but to recover and avoid emissions in areas with high density of farms exceeding the emissions levels allowed. Then they identified the potential as nutrient source and started doing some studies on the fertilising potential.
- Live Ammonia trapping: <http://ammoniatrapping.com/> → Ongoing. Optimisation of technology to bring the technology to a commercial level. Scaleup and concentration of the final product.
- Walnut project. <https://walnutproject.eu/> (Also UGENT). Several pilots under development regarding the obtention of fertilising products from wastewater, brine etc. Each pilot works with different side streams.

ItaCyL is specialised in treatment and extraction technologies.

Waste streams they work with:

- Livestock waste, mainly slurry.
- Some experience in wastewater from agrifood industries (dairy)

Attributes discussed:

Opportunities:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• These type of extraction technologies open up a great opportunity regarding alternative nutrient sources. Even though these are not producing final fertilising products, the outcomes can be used by fertilising companies as inputs.• Technology can be used to recover and offset excess of nutrients in areas sensitive to N emissions.• Different products can be attained by changing the parameters / inputs used in the process (type of acid used). <p>Threads:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of knowledge and uncertainties on the certification and regulatory frameworks. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Technology discussed under development stage. Unknown interest by the industry.• Final product is (for now) very diluted and shall be concentrated in order to be able to manage it efficiently. <p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cost-effective process; large amount of waste available across Europe.
ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED	
LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE	

ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• They would like to keep posted about NOVAFERT outcomes -> send link to subscribe to newsletter.• They would like to remain available for future collaborations and any question that might arise.• Transfer the elements of the matrix to the rest of the partners of the consortia, in case of relevance for them (to be done once all interviews are done).

CATALAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING			
EVENT	Personal interview		
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	19/06/2023 – 14.30 CEST – Online		
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Carmen Galindo – EIT Food		
PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)	ETSIAAB - UPM	Profesor Contratado Doctor (Associated Professor)	Higher Education

DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES

Guillermo Guardia is Associated Professor at the Chemistry Department of ETSIAAB (UPM, Madrid, Spain). His group has been studying impacts of nitrogen fertilisation, specially related to GHG emissions.

Order of the day:

- (EIT Food & UPM) Presentation round about UPM and EIT Food.
- (EIT Food) Introduction of NOVAFERT project & scope of the meeting.
- (UPM) Experience on the use / development / study of alternative fertilising products.
- (EIT Food & UPM) Identification of SWOT attributes for agreed waste streams – wastewater, sludge, animal manure, digestate, biowaste, organic by-products.

Minutes:

Short summary of EIT Food and our role in NOVAFERT provided by EIT Food.

Short summary of the goals of NOVAFERT project provided by EIT Food.

Summary of Guillermo Guardia's activities: he is part of COAPA research group (<https://ceigram.upm.es/grupos-de-investigacion/contaminacion-de-agrosistemas-por-practicas-agricolas-coapa/>) focusing on ecosystem pollution, within the Chemistry department of ETSIAAB and CEIGRAM (<https://ceigram.upm.es/en/>).

Most of the work done is around evaluation on the nitrogen fertilisation impacts, around GHG emissions, as well as emissions of reactive gases (?) such as N acids or ammonia.

They work on building knowledge around emission mechanisms of different fertilising products, small and medium scale through modelling and long term studies.

Evaluation made on different irrigation systems, different types of fertilising products (synthetic, organic, use of nitrification inhibitors), and different management systems (timing, dosage, conservation agriculture)

Secondary raw materials / organic fertilising products used:

Sludge (few), slurry, manure from different animals.

Attributes for SWOT – general comment of ORGANIC FERTILISING

Strengths:

- Potential to reduce GHG emission upstream the value chain – considering LCA and carbon footprint of synthetic fertilising.
- Opportunities to reduce carbon footprint of the agrifood value chain (reduction of upstream Carbon footprint)
- Some side streams (i.e., manure, compost, biochar) can also contribute to carbon sequestration, which is very much desired to offset other emissions.

Weaknesses:

- High diversity of raw materials and waste streams (for organic fertilising products), difficulty homogenising and regulating its application -. Different emissions' profiles, agronomical performance, composition, etc.
- Varying composition of the different organic fertilising sources / raw materials. This means for example that, if you fertilise based on the N content, you might end up applying excess in phosphorous (pollution...) or, if you fertilise based on P, then you might have less N than needed.

- Regional management of waste streams. Availability of waste streams shall be considered at a local level. And end user operating in different regions might need to adapt their fertilising strategy locally, depending on the availability of resources in the region. Transportation of some waste streams / alternative fertilising products might reduce economic and environmental feasibility.

Opportunities:

- Use of secondary raw materials from organic sources (i.e. Ammonia extracted from manure, as explained during ItaCyL's interview on Life Green Ammonia) can be interesting to supplement deficit in N from different nutrient sources.
- Opportunity within European policies, fully aligned.
- Potential improvement of cost-benefit for end users (when well managed).

Threads:

- For optimising the use of organic fertilising products you need to have a good understanding of the nutrient release patterns... otherwise you might have: (a) excess of N not used at the end of the season, and therefore leakage; (b) lower dosage than needed, and therefore lower yields.
- Organic doesn't necessarily mean lower emission than synthetic fertilising products (in terms of direct emissions), e.g. slurry when not well managed.

**ADDITIONAL MATERIAL
TO BE INCLUDED**

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.	
NEXT STEPS (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Share information about the SWOT analysis with relevant partners within NOVAFERT's partners.• Guillermo agrees on a follow up in case any of the partners wants to dive deeper into the points identified.

CATALAN REGIONAL WORKING GROUP EVENTS REPORTING		
EVENT	4 th RWG meeting in the frame of a technical day organized together with the Department of Climate Action from Catalonia and the Fertimanure project.	
DATE AND LOCATION (if applicable)	18-10-2023, Vic, (Spain)	
FACILITATOR (consortium partner)	Ana Robles Aguilar (BETA Tech Center)	
	BETA	Researcher
		Researcher

PARTICIPANT(S) (add as many rows as needed)			Farmer
	Cobirgy		Farmer
			Technic
			Technic
			Agriculture specialist
			Agriculture specialist
	Regional Government		Environmental specialist
			Environmental specialist
			Environmental specialist
	Apergas		Energy specialist
	Adial		Consultancy livestock
	Beta	Researcher	Researcher
	Friselva		Researcher
	Beta	Communication officer	Communication

	Beta	Reseacher	Researcher
	Beta	Researcher	Researcher
	Beta	Researcher	Researcher
	Beta	Researcher	Researcher
			Other
	FCAC		Other
	Regional Government		Other
	Beta	Researcher	Other
			Other
			Other
			Other

		Other
	Labin	Other
	Regional Government	Other
		Other
	Cooperativa Plana de Vic	Other
	Agrocat	Other
	Labin	Other
	Gap cooperativa	Other
	Regional government	Other

			Other
			Company
			Other
	Beta	Deputy Director	Researcher
	Beta	Director	Researcher
	Beta	Researcher	Researcher
DESCRIPTION OF THE MEETING CONTENTS AND MAIN OUTCOMES	<p>About fifty people participated in a PATT Conference on new bio fertiliser products recovered from livestock manure, organised by the UVic-UCC BETA Technology Centre. The aim was to discuss about Technical considerations and regulatory framework of Bio fertilisers made from nutrients recovered from livestock manure. The event took place in the Gothic Hall of the UVic, and brought together various actors interested in the valorisation of livestock manure to show some of the latest advances obtained in European projects underway in this field, as is the case of NOVAFERT and FERTIMANURE.</p>		
	<p>The initial part of the PATT Conference (Annual Technology Transfer Plan) gave way to presentations by several representatives of the Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda (DACCC). These interventions served to review the trends that the livestock sector across Europe is following to process and valorise the manure, but also to outline the actions that are being carried out in Catalonia with the aim to improve fertilisation practices, always with an eye on the climate neutrality objectives to be achieved by 2030 and 2050. Afterwards, the deputy director of CT BETA and coordinator of the FERTIMANURE project, Laia Llenas, presented the bio fertiliser products obtained</p>		

in the five biorefineries that this project has built in several European countries, and whose agronomic performance is being studied, if it fits with the current regulation and the real market exit potential.

After that, CT BETA researchers Ana Robles and Jorge Senán introduced the NOVAFERT project, which has already begun work to demonstrate the technical, economic and environmental viability of a wide portfolio of alternative bio fertiliser products recovered from various types of organic waste.

The day's program was completed by the intervention of a representative of the company Sun Chemical Services, around the regulatory framework that affects these new products, and a presentation on their potential application in organic agriculture by Nagore Guerra and Ricard Carreras, CT BETA researchers.

Finally, a participatory activity was carried out with the attendees to determine their perception and acceptance of the new bio fertiliser products after presenting the results of the SWOT analyses carried out by the NOVAFERT project, to finalise with the possibility of traveling to Muntanyola to visit a pilot biorefinery.

The annual program of Jornades PATT is one of the instruments of reference for the transfer of knowledge, training and capacity building in the agri-food and forestry sector in Catalonia. Coordinated by the DACC, each year it has the collaboration of more than 250 entities and organisations from these sectors, companies, universities and research centers and other administrations.

This event was useful to receive feedback on the swot analysis made for the Catalan region, and reach out to new farmers and companies to be considered living labs and case studies for the LCA.

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ADDITIONAL MATERIAL TO BE INCLUDED

LINKS (if any) TO THE RELATED PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, ANNOUNCEMENTS IN THE ORGANISERS' WEBSITE, ETC.

[Beta Tech Center — Biofertilizants en base a nutrients recuperats de dejeccions ramaderes: Consideracions tècniques i marc normatiu.](#)

[Biofertilizants en base a nutrients recuperats de dejeccions ramaderes - U-Divulga \(uvic.cat\) .
get file \(gencat.cat\) .](#)

[BETA Tech Center en X: " Produir #biofertilizants a partir de nutrients recuperats de la valorització de dejeccions ramaderes pot ajudar a resoldre el repte de la gestió d'excedents. Aquests nous productes són competitius en el mercat? N'hem parlat amb el sector a #Vic. https://t.co/oqem05YOfM https://t.co/xskWJAQA13" / X \(twitter.com\) .](#)

[El CT BETA organitza una jornada PATT a Vic sobre biofertilizants recuperats a partir de dejeccions ramaderes | L'apunt \(uvic.cat\) .](#)

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NEXT STEPS (if any)

The outcomes of the workshop were considered to fine tune the SWOT analyses made for the Catalan region.

Some interesting companies from the sector were identified, and they will be contacted to be studied as possible living labs from the region.

